

Clinical Profile and Management Outcomes of Cesarean Scar Ectopic Pregnancy: A Cross-Sectional Study from a Tertiary Care Center

Authors:

Dr. Praneta Chandnani¹, Dr. Vishal Chaudhari², Dr. Anupriya Maharshi³, Dr. Vrushali Jadhav⁴

¹Junior resident Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, MGM Medical college and Hospital, Chh. Sambhajinagar, Maharashtra, India.

²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, MGM Medical college and Hospital, Chh. Sambhajinagar, Maharashtra, India.

³Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, MGM Medical college and Hospital, Chh. Sambhajinagar, Maharashtra, India.

⁴Junior Resident, MGM Medical College, Aurangabad, India.

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Vishal Chaudhari, Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, MGM Medical college and Hospital, Chh. Sambhajinagar, Maharashtra, India.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19688247>

Received: 28-March-2026, Accepted: 13-April-2026, Online First: 17-April-2026

ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Scar ectopic pregnancy (SEP) is a life-threatening condition where an embryo implants within the myometrium of a previous uterine scar. With an incidence of approximately 1 in 2,000 pregnancies, it is an increasingly common cause of maternal morbidity. **Materials and Methods:** This cross-sectional study at MGM Medical College (Nov 2023–Jan 2025) analyzed 12 patients with confirmed SEP. Clinical profiles, β -HCG levels, and ultrasound findings were recorded to determine management strategies. **Results:** The mean patient age was 30.25 years, with all subjects having a history of at least one Caesarean section (LSCS). The most common symptom was vaginal bleeding (41%), though 33% of patients were asymptomatic. Mean gestational age was 8.3 weeks, and mean β -HCG was 40,960 mIU/mL. Ultrasound classified the majority of cases as Type II (66.7%). Management included diagnostic laparoscopy with suction evacuation (38.4%), laparoscopic excision (23%), and one case (7.6%) requiring a hysterectomy due to scar rupture. **Conclusion:** Early diagnosis via transvaginal ultrasound is critical. A history of multiple LSCS correlates with higher risk, necessitating specialized, individualized management to prevent catastrophic outcomes like uterine rupture.

Keywords: Cesarean scar pregnancy, Ectopic pregnancy, β -hCG, Laparoscopy, Methotrexate

INTRODUCTION:

Scar ectopic pregnancy is an increasingly recognized, life-threatening condition where the embryo implants within the myometrium and fibrous tissue of a previous uterine scar. Reviews cite the incidence of Cesarean Scar Pregnancy to approximate 1 in 2000 pregnancies, and is increasing. Scar ectopic pregnancies have become a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in fertile women. This pregnancy is abnormal from the start and hence requires specialized management(1)

Many conditions that affect the shape or structure of the uterus, such as bicornuate uterus or uterine septum also increases the risk of scar ectopic pregnancy(2).

Diagnosis of scar ectopic pregnancy is challenging, symptoms of scar ectopic pregnancy are similar to normal pregnancy(3) All women with a previous uterine

surgery presenting with symptoms of ectopic pregnancy (vaginal bleeding, pain in abdomen) should have high suspicion of scar ectopic(4) Tests to diagnose ectopic pregnancy include Urine pregnancy tests, Ultrasound and Serum β HCG, where transvaginal ultrasound gives earlier diagnosis than transabdominal ultrasound. Ultrasound is used to look for the location, size of the gestational sac, the presence of fetal cardiac activity, and the thickness of the myometrium around the scar(5)

Ultrasound criteria is used diagnose caesarean scar pregnancy as described in RCOG guidelines:

1. Empty uterine cavity.
2. Gestational sac or solid mass of trophoblast located anteriorly at the level of the internal-os embedded at the

site of the previous lower uterine segment caesarean section scar.

3. Thin or absent layer of myometrium between the gestational sac and the bladder.
4. Evidence of prominent trophoblastic/placental circulation on Doppler examination.
5. Empty endocervical canal.(6)

On the basis of these two optimizing thresholds of anterior myometrial thickness and Gestational sac diameter(GSD), for more practical clinical diagnosis and application, caesarean scar ectopic pregnancy is classified.(7)

TABLE 1; Clinical classification of CSEP and recommended individual treatment strategy (8)

Practical clinical classification	Anterior Myometrium Thickness(mm)	Average diameter of the Gestational Sac or Mass(mm)	Surgical Treatment Strategy Recommended
Type I	Greater than 3mm		Suction curettage with or without Hysteroscopy* under ultrasound guidance
Type II	1-3mm	IIa: 30mm or less	Suction Curettage with Hysteroscopy* under ultrasound guidance
		IIb: Greater than 30mm	Hysteroscopy with laparoscopic monitoring or excision^ or transvaginal excision
Type III	1 or less	IIIa : 50 mm or less	Laparoscopic excision or transvaginal excision
		IIIb : Greater than 50mm or with UAVF	Laparoscopic excision after UAE or Laparotomy

UAVF- uterine arteriovenous fistulae, UAE- uterine artery embolization.

Hysteroscopy is used to evaluate whether products of conception have been removed completely, with hysteroscopic resection of residual products when indicated.

During laparoscopy, if the products of conception could not be removed completely, haemorrhage occurred, or myometrial layer bulge or thin- appearing myometrium was found, laparoscopic excision with scar defect repair was performed.

Injection Methotrexate It stops the cell from dividing by binding to dihydrofolate reductase blocking the reduction of dihydrofolate to tetrahydrofolate (active form of folic acid). As a result thymidylate synthetase and various steps in de novo purine synthesis are halted leading to arrest of DNA, RNA and protein synthesis. and can be given intrasac or local or intramuscular or intravenous.(8)

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This was a hospital-based cross-sectional observational study conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at MGM Medical College and Hospital, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar, Maharashtra, India. The

study was carried out over a period of 14 months from November 2023 to January 2025.

Study Population:

All women diagnosed with cesarean scar ectopic pregnancy (CSEP) during the study period and presenting to the tertiary care center were included in the study. Due to the rarity of the condition, all eligible cases encountered during the study duration were enrolled.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Women with confirmed diagnosis of cesarean scar ectopic pregnancy
- Patients diagnosed based on clinical findings, serum β-hCG levels, and ultrasonographic evaluation
- Patients willing to provide informed consent

Exclusion Criteria:

- Women with other types of ectopic pregnancies (e.g., tubal, ovarian, cervical)
- Patients with incomplete medical records

Diagnostic Criteria:

The diagnosis of cesarean scar ectopic pregnancy was established based on transvaginal ultrasonography findings in accordance with standard diagnostic criteria, including:

- Empty uterine cavity
- Empty endocervical canal
- Gestational sac located anteriorly at the level of the internal os, embedded in the previous cesarean scar
- Thin or absent myometrium between the gestational sac and the urinary bladder
- Increased peritrophoblastic vascularity on Doppler examination

Serum β -hCG levels were measured at the time of diagnosis for all patients.

Data Collection:

Data were collected from indoor case records using a structured data collection form. The following variables were recorded:

- Demographic details (age)
- Obstetric history (gravidity, parity, number of previous cesarean sections)
- Presenting complaints (vaginal bleeding, abdominal pain, asymptomatic)
- Gestational age at diagnosis
- Serum β -hCG levels at presentation
- Ultrasonographic findings including gestational sac size, myometrial thickness, and presence or absence of fetal cardiac activity
- Type of cesarean scar pregnancy based on clinical classification
- Management modality employed

Classification of Cases:

Cases were classified into Type I, Type II (IIa and IIb), and Type III (IIIa and IIIb) based on anterior myometrial thickness and gestational sac diameter, as per established clinical classification systems.

Management Protocol:

All patients were assessed for hemodynamic stability.

- **Medical Management:** Hemodynamically stable patients without evidence of rupture were offered medical management with methotrexate (1 mg/kg body weight) administered on alternate days, along with folinic acid (0.1 mg/kg body weight) rescue therapy. Serial

monitoring of serum β -hCG levels and ultrasonography was performed.

- **Surgical Management:** Patients who were hemodynamically unstable, had significant vaginal bleeding, suspected uterine rupture, or failed medical management underwent surgical intervention. Surgical procedures included:
 - Ultrasound-guided suction and evacuation
 - Laparoscopy-guided suction evacuation
 - Hysteroscopy-guided evacuation
 - Laparoscopic scar excision and repair
 - Emergency hysterectomy in cases of rupture

The choice of management was individualized based on clinical presentation, ultrasound findings, and surgeon discretion.

Outcome Measures:

The primary outcome measures included clinical presentation, diagnostic parameters, and management strategies employed. Secondary outcomes included complications such as hemorrhage, need for hysterectomy, and intraoperative blood loss.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were entered and analyzed using Microsoft Excel. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Ethical Considerations:

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee prior to the commencement of the study. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality of patient data was strictly maintained throughout the study.

Reporting Guidelines:

This study was conducted and reported in accordance with the STROBE (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology) guidelines.

RESULTS:

12 patients with cesarean scar ectopic pregnancy were identified and included in the study period after applying exclusion criteria.

The results were analyzed between those who had bleeding per vaginum and those who did not. Differences in age, gravidity, parity, number of previous Cesarean deliveries, β -hcg levels and presence of fetal cardiac activity on USG were observed.

Patient demographic and clinical profile:

Table 2: Age Distribution of Patients (n=12)

AGE (in years)	NO OF CASES (n=12)	PERCENTAGES
<19	0	
19-25	3	25%
26-30	2	16.7%
30-35	5	41%
>35	2	16.7

Table 3 : Presenting complaints of cases

PRESENTING COMPLAINTS	NO OF CASES (n=12)	PERCENTAGES
Vaginal bleeding	5	41%
Pain in abdomen	2	16%
Vomiting	1	8.3%
Incomplete abortion	1	8.3%
No complaints	3	33%

Mean Age noted was 30.25 years. Age Ranges from the youngest patient was 20 and the oldest was 43. The concentration being the majority of patients (approx. 58%) fall within the 20–33 age bracket, which aligns with peak reproductive years.

Asymptomatic, 3 out of 12 recorded cases (33%) reported "No complaints," emphasizing the importance of routine ultrasound in high-risk patients. Vaginal Bleeding was the most common symptom (41%), ranging from spotting to heavy bleeding. Also, severe Complications with one patient presented in hypovolemic shock, and another presented with severe abdominal pain and vomiting, later diagnosed with a ruptured uterine scar.

Graph 1 : Gestational age distribution

Gestational Age-Average: 8.3 weeks. Ranges is presenting as early as 6.2 weeks and as late as 11.2 weeks. Therefore requiring Early diagnosis is critical to prevent uterine rupture.

Graph 2: Distribution of previous LSCS

Plot diagram: Comparison between initial β -hcg levels and Gestational age

Obstetric History (Previous LSCS) was seen every patient in this dataset had a history of at least one Lower Segment Cesarean Section (LSCS). 33% had 1 previous LSCS, 50% had 2, and 17% had 3. This confirms the direct correlation between previous uterine surgery and the risk of scar ectopic pregnancy. Diagnostic Biomarkers and Imaging used were Initial β -hcg Levels and the mean β -hcg was 40,960 mIU/mL. There was high variability (Standard Deviation: 34,675), with levels ranging from 2,900 to over 107,000 mIU/mL.

Table 4: Distribution of cases according to classification

Type I	>3mm	1
Type IIa	1-3mm + G sac or mass <3cm .	4
Type IIb	1-3mm + G sac > 3cms	4
Type IIIa	<1mm + <5cms G sac or mass.	2
Type IIIb	< 1mm + >5cms Gsac or mass.	1

Ultrasound Findings (USG) was used to classify them, with myometrial Thickness which was the key measurements of the residual myometrial thickness between the gestational sac and the bladder ranged from 0.9mm to 9mm. Lower measurements (e.g., <2mm) were associated with higher risks of rupture. The fetal Cardiac activity was present in 50% of the patients. The presence of cardiac activity generally correlated with higher β -hcg levels (mean >70,000 for positive cases).

Graph 3: Management strategies used

Also, 38.4% of patients were managed with diagnostic laparoscopy with Suction and evacuation. 23% needed laparoscopic excision of scar pregnancy. It was observed that laparoscopic scar excision has a wide range of blood loss values, while USG guided suction and evacuation had relatively lower blood loss. 7.6% patient had to undergo hysterectomy due to rupture of scar.

DISCUSSION:

Caesarean scar ectopic pregnancy (CSEP) is a rare but increasingly common complication of previous uterine surgery. As a leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality, its management requires a specialized, multidisciplinary approach. Findings indicate that the majority of CSEP cases (50%) are diagnosed between 6

and 8 weeks of gestation, highlighting a critical window for intervention. While some patients remain asymptomatic, the most frequent presentation was vaginal bleeding (58%), followed by abdominal pain (25%). The lack of pathognomonic signs underscores the reliance on high-resolution transvaginal ultrasound (TVUS) and serum β -hCG levels for diagnosis. Transvaginal sonography remains the gold standard, particularly for identifying key markers such as an empty uterine cavity and a gestational sac embedded within the anterior myometrial defect.

Management strategies are largely dictated by hemodynamic stability, gestational sac diameter (GSD), and β -hCG levels. While medical management with Methotrexate (MTX) is a viable first-line therapy for stable patients effectively arresting DNA synthesis to stop cell division our study suggests a strong leaning toward surgical intervention for definitive treatment. Specifically, 38.4% of patients were successfully managed with diagnostic laparoscopy followed by suction and evacuation, which showed relatively lower blood loss compared to other methods. However, higher-risk cases required laparoscopic excision of the scar (23%), and in severe instances of scar rupture, hysterectomy was necessary (7.6%).

The classification of CSEP into types I, II, and III based on anterior myometrial thickness provides a practical framework for clinical application. As scar thickness decreases (Type III), the risk of rupture increases, often necessitating more aggressive surgical measures over medical management.

Literature Comparison:

Our findings are comparable to studies by Rajeswari et al., where vaginal bleeding was the most common presenting symptom.

LIMITATIONS:

This study has certain limitations including small sample size and single-center design, which may limit the generalizability of the findings.

However, it provides valuable insight into early diagnosis and management strategies in a tertiary care setting.

CONCLUSION:

Cesarean scar ectopic pregnancy remains a significant diagnostic and management challenge. Early detection through transvaginal ultrasound and β -hCG monitoring is essential to prevent life-threatening complications such as uterine rupture and massive haemorrhage. While medical management with Methotrexate serves

as an important tool for stable, early-stage cases, surgical interventions—particularly laparoscopy-guided procedures—offer effective resolution with manageable morbidity. The choice of treatment must be tailored to the individual's clinical stability, ultrasound classification, and future fertility desires. Standardized protocols and increased clinical awareness are paramount to improving outcomes in this high-risk obstetric population.

Further large-scale multicentric studies are recommended to establish standardized management protocols.

This study was reported in accordance with STROBE guidelines.

REFERENCES:

1. Rajeswari KSR, Anushri M, Shaunthani P. (2023) Cesarean scar pregnancy: diagnostic dilemma. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol* ;12:3692-4.
2. Pędraszewski, P.; Właźlak, E.; Panek, W.; Surkont, G. Cesarean Scar Pregnancy—A New Challenge for Obstetricians. *J. Ultrason.* 2018, 18, 56–62.
3. Getaneh Tadesse, W. Cesarean Scar Ectopic Pregnancy. In *Non-Tubal Ectopic Pregnancy*; IntechOpen: London, UK, 2020.
4. Haddaden, M.; Maharaj, A.; Muzzi, K.; Paudel, K.; Haas, C.J. A Large Unruptured Ectopic Pregnancy. *Radiol. Case Rep.* 2021, 16, 1204–1206.
5. Bozkurt, D.K.; Bozkurt, M.; Sahin, L. Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Addition to Ultrasound in the Diagnosis of Cesarean Scar Ectopic Pregnancy. *J. Med. Cases* 2014, 5, 329–333.
6. Rajeswari KSR, Anushri M, Shaunthani P. Cesarean scar pregnancy: diagnostic dilemma. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol* 2023;12:3692-4
7. Jameel, K., Abdul Mannan, G. E., Niaz, R., & Hayat, D. E. (2021). Cesarean Scar Ectopic Pregnancy: A Diagnostic and Management Challenge. *Cureus*, 13(4), e14463. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.14463>
8. Ban, Y., Shen, J., Wang, X., et al. (2023). Cesarean Scar Ectopic Pregnancy Clinical Classification System With Recommended Surgical Strategy. *Obstetrics and gynecology*, 141(5), 927–936. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AOG.0000000000005113>